

Bursting tests of a short fibre reinforced composite air intake manifold

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SUMMARY

The air intake manifold of a gasoline engine made by short glass fibre reinforced plastic was considered and its mechanical behaviour during a bursting test was studied.

The aim of the work was to investigate the influence of material anisotropy, due to manufacturing process, and of vibration welding parameter process to the overall component resistance.

Keywords: short fibre composite, burst test, failure analysis

INTRODUCTION

In the automotive industry there is a high demand of lower density materials according to the engine downsize policy, energy saving and costs reduction.

Composite materials have this characteristic while ensuring a good mechanical strength and sufficient durability; moreover they provide a substantial noise reduction and vibrations absorption.

These materials they replaced metals (in particular aluminium) in many components, such as air intake manifolds, air filter housings, timing gears and radiator fans.

In particular in air intake application it was done to improve the performance through a smoother internal surface of the intake manifold. In fact low roughness values (from Ra 5 to Ra 1.6 up to 0.4 by mould polishing) are easily obtainable (Fig.1a-b).

Fig. 1-a Roughness of a thermoplastic inner runner surface

Fig. 1-b Roughness of an aluminum inner runner surface

The component under study was an air intake manifold (AIM) used in automotive engines. Its main role is to convey air in the engine cylinders in order to achieve an optimum combustion. In particular the AIM function includes the replacement of working fluid in each cylinder, its filling with filtered air and the reduction of the noise caused by pressure waves during the refilling and discharge phases. The component design key issues are a low weight, an adequate mechanical strength, the durability and as much as possible reduced overall size [1]. Traditional solutions for AIM manufacturing are based on aluminium alloy casting; nevertheless the introduction of

plastics simplified the AIM design process providing the engineers with more freedom in the choice of the shape. At the same time the use of plastics for AIM manufacturing contributed to enhance both power and economical performances of automotive engines [1-5]. In particular five major benefits from plastics AIM can be highlighted: (i) improvement of engine performance through a smoother internal surface of the intake manifold, in particular an increase in air flow capacity of about 3% can be obtained which can result in an increase in the peak power up to 3%, compared with their metal equivalents; (ii) improvement in both fuel consumption and the quality of base emission through improved combustion efficiency due to the thermal insulation effect; (iii) weight reduction up to 50%, respect to conventional sand cast aluminium manifolds; (iv) noise reduction by means of the vibration damping effect of plastic material used; (v) cost reduction through improved productivity.

Two processes can be adopted to manufacture plastic AIMs: lost core moulding and vibration welding [1,5]. In lost core moulding, the reinforced polymer is moulded over a low-melt temperature tin–bismuth alloy [2-5]. After polymer solidification, the over-moulded core is melted out and re-used. The major disadvantages of the lost core moulding process are the high capital cost and the complexity associated with metal alloy processing. In contrast, the vibration welding technique provides automotive parts suppliers with a simpler and more robust manufacturing process with lower capital investment [2-5]. Vibration welding, in fact, is a common technique for joining injection moulded thermoplastic parts. It consists in bringing two parts together under a weld pressure, and then making one of the parts vibrate at a specific frequency over a peak-to-peak amplitude. The energy dissipated by friction and viscous shear stresses melts the polymer at the weld interface. The molten polymer is then forced from the interface as the two parts come together (meltdown). When a preset meltdown depth is reached, the vibration is stopped. The welding parameters used are: 240Hz frequency, 1,6 mm amplitude e three different pressures and durations in the different stages: friction pressure 65bar for 1,8 s, welding pressure 110bar for 1,8 s and cooling pressure 95 bar for 1,5 s. So the total time of welding was 6,1 s.

As a matter of industrial practice the most used process for plastic AIMs manufacturing is based on the vibration welding technique. The materials used for AIMs manufacturing are typically short-fibre reinforced plastic (SFRP) and in particular glass fibre are the most common reinforcement (Fig2) [8].

Fig. 2 short glass fiber at SEM

The use of SFRP allows to design and to manufacture manifold parts able to resist under severe working conditions including highly variable temperature, high random gradients of internal pressure and mechanical shocks.

The welded surfaces represent a weak area of the assembled manifold from a structural point of view [5]. In particular, in the welded edges and in the neighboring regions the following phenomena can significantly change the mechanical performances: fibre redistribution (some fibres can be pushed or pulled out either in some cases fibres are locally aligned causing a local tensile strength reduction), matrix inhomogeneity (vibration welding can change the amorphous phase percentage in the melted matrix) and matrix burnings. (Fig.3)

Fig. 3 analysis of weld surface with microscope

Nowadays the purpose of the studies on plastic AIMs is to define the optimal design and manufacturing conditions in order to achieve higher component quality and reliability respect to available solutions [6,7]. Three major classes of variables influence the welded mechanical performances: the component geometry, the material and the parameters of the vibration welding process. In particular as regards the geometrical parameters, the most important are the wall thickness and radius, with special care to the fillet radius. The melt polymer viscosity, density, polymer melting latent heat and heat capacity are the main material parameters that influence the weld quality. The welding process parameters that have to be taken into account are the pressure, the duration and the vibration amplitude and frequency. In previous works some process parameters were taken into account, but most of works did not consider their interactions. So, for example, it was found that a reduced value of the holding pressure during the welding process can increase the weld tensile strength, on the other side it was seen that

increased values of vibration frequency marginally increased the weld strength. Nevertheless from industrial point of view the overall combination of all these parameters has to be accounted in order to obtain high weld quality in a suitable production time. In the present work we started investigating the influence of the interaction of holding pressure and vibration parameters, amplitude and frequency, to the final quality of the welded area in the case of a special model of AIM.

The combination of holding pressure, vibration frequency and amplitude were not investigated together. The raw material consisted in composite plastic pellets made by glass fibre embedded in Polyamide 6 polymeric matrix. Validation tests of the AIMs require the verification of components resistance to thermal and mechanical loads. In the work the analysis of air intake manifold failures occurred during dedicated mechanical tests called bursting tests is present.

Materials and Methods

The air intake manifold under study is a Magneti Marelli Powertrain's component developed for a 3 cylinders gasoline engine. The component is the base on which a number of other devices are hold. All of these devices compose the air intake system for the air suction and the fuel and oxygen mixing inside the combustion chamber. The most important components fixed on it are: the throttle body that controls the air flux into the engine; the exhaust gas engine recirculation unit (EGR) that brings a portion of the engine's exhaust gas back to the engine cylinders to dilute the mix with inert gas, lowering the adiabatic flame temperature and reducing the production of NO_x; the air filter which removes solid particulates such as dust, pollen, mold and fuel rail used to deliver the fuel into the combustion chamber.

Due to complexity and crucial function of this component, its importance and its role in engine efficiency and safety, a great number of quality tests and in particular explosion-like test are required.

These tests are performed according to a Magneti Marelli internal standard and to specific costumers requests.

Except otherwise specified, the test environment and fluid must have the following characteristics: temperature (23 ± 5 °C), atmospheric pressure (101 kPa), relative humidity (up to 50 %) and test fluid (air). Before the tests are carried out, the parts must be conditioned according to ASTM D618 standard.

The conditioning process consists on exposing to the air for 24h at 23°C with terms of 50% of humidity due to the high material's hygroscopy.

As said, the material of the air intake manifold is a reinforced polyamide 6. Generally speaking, reinforced polyamide is a very tough material, with excellent all-round chemical resistance. It is most commonly reinforced with glass fibre, either short or long, in order to improve the material mechanical properties (e.g. stiffness and strength). The addition of glass fibre, however, tends to reduce the impact strength of reinforced material [10]. To overcome this problem, an elastomeric component is often added.

High fibre contents are possible, giving particularly good heat resistance. Materials in the nylon family have relatively high moisture absorption, so they require drying before moulding. Dimensional stability and tolerances can be affected by moisture absorption in the first few days of service, reaching equilibrium at about 2.7 wt% moisture content in air at 50% relative humidity and about 9-10% in water.

Component under study was made using as reinforcement short (150 μm to 200 μm) glass fibre; the presence of these fibres provokes a certain degree of anisotropy in the material behaviour.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of molded and welded SF-RP polyamide 6 material

	Young Modulus (MPa) ISO 527	Strenght at break (MPa) ISO 527	Poisson ratio
Molded material	6000	110	0.39
Welded material	1200	50	0.45

The mechanical properties of the molded material are summarized in table 1, referred to the conditioned material

Burst test description and results

The validation and industrialization of the component require several tests that ensure the proper functioning under certain conditions: storage temperature ($-40 \div +130$ °C), air temperature in the engine compartment ($-30 \div +130$ °C), aspirated air temperature ($-30 \div +80$ °C), temperature of EGR flange at $+130$ °C (max value).

To have resistance to all the mechanical failures that may suffer the components connected to it.

The identification of structural faults or weaknesses in any joints due to design and/or process errors is done by checking the strength of the air intake manifold.

The test method consists in assembling the air intake manifold with all its components, plug the remaining interfaces including the throttle body air intake and the engine flange, which must be connected to a rigid blank flange, then fill the manifold with fluid (for example, injector flushing fluid of the type Exol D40) and gradually increase the pressure, with a speed of 10kPa/s, until the manifold bursts, that is, until the part brakes and there is a leak of fluid.

In this case the bursting pressure of the manifold must not be lower than 1MPa but the result on this component was of a burst pressure of 0.84 MPa (fig 4 a-b).

Fig. 4-a: AIM before test

Fig. 4-b: AIM after burst test

After observation with different types of survey instruments e.g. optical microscope and SEM, the appearance of the area affected is that of a flat plate by the rather irregular contour, and the fracture appears to have originated on the welding line (fig 5-a-b-c).

Fig. 5-a-b-c different image of failure zone with different resolution and instruments (digital photo,microscope,SEM)

FEM analysis

In failure analysis it is necessary to first check if there is a design error about the wall thickness of the component.

To verify the stresses that arise from the burst test of the air intake manifold a careful analysis through the use of Finite element analysis with the FEM commercial code Ansys was made.

Mesh grid on design model for simulation was prepared with Hypermesh.

Fig. 6

After FEM analysis it was possible to affirm that there are no particular problems in the integrity of any components.

In the Bottom Cover it is possible to observe the presence of large zones in which stresses values (~100MPa) are close to 110 MPa, which is maximum static strength of reinforced polyamide 6. High and possibly critical stress values can be observed in correspondence of ribs, but such values are in exterior zones of ribs so that the risk of failure due to them is moderately low (fig 7).

Fig. 7: Von Mises stresses in bottom cover

In welding lines it is possible to observe that stresses evaluated do not reveal particular problems to component integrity. Maximum result value of stress was 34MPa (fig.8), that is lower than the allowable strength of the material in the welded surfaces (50MPa). Mechanical characteristic assigned to the material after vibration welding represent a worst case for this analysis.

Fig. 8: Von Mises stresses on weld lines

Since in burst experimental test bottom cover results critical, ribs and fillets have been introduced to reduce stresses in components (Fig. 9).

In following images we report modified parts with relative introduced elements.

Fig. 9: Ribs and fillets introduced to reduce stresses.

FEM analysis highlighted that modifying the component geometry by changing the position or adding fillet and ribs an overall stress reduction was not obtained, on the contrary, maximum stress values observed in the initial geometry just were just moved: the model with inner and outer fillets present higher stresses in the upper cover and reduced stresses in the bottom cover (Tab 2)

Tabella 1 simulation results after the design review.

Model	Bottom cover	Upper cover
With fillets	98MPa	79MPa
Without fillets	100 MPa	61 MPa

Conclusion

The common practice of adding ribs and fillets to the existing model gave no improvement to the stress state, so it is necessary to review all parameters in manufacturing process (like vibration frequency and holding pressure to improve component joints) the CAD and CAE model to remove critical geometrical features.

A better knowledge of the material is necessary to reduce weight and cost production without decrease mechanical strength.

The combination of all these variables represents the know-how for manufacturing of these mechanical components and suggests experimental testing to optimize the product.

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